

5th

ANNUAL
REPORT

*for the period
ending June 30,
1961*

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, Inc.

HARVARD
COLLEGE
LIBRARY

THE LIBRARY OF

BROWN UNIVERSITY

IN MEMORY OF

GIVEN BY

CORNELL COLLEGE MEMORIAL BOOKS COLLECTION

THE MASSACHUSETTS
HISTORICAL SOCIETY

LIBRARY OF HENRY ADAMS
GIVEN BY BROOKS AND
CHARLES FRANCIS ADAMS
JANUARY IX MCMXIX

THE LIBRARY

RESIDENCE HALLS
COLLECTION

THE LIBRARY COMPANY
OF PHILADELPHIA

Communiter Bona profundere Deum est

COLLEGE FOR WOMEN
LIBRARY

PURCHASED FROM FINES

5th ANNUAL REPORT

for the period ending June 30, 1961

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, *Inc.*
1025 CONNECTICUT AVENUE, N. W. WASHINGTON 6, D. C.

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* Dr. Keeney served as a member of the Executive Committee through December 7, 1960. He has been succeeded by Mr. Black.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

The Council on Library Resources

THE FIRST FIVE YEARS

About this time, our club meeting, not at a tavern, but in a little room of Mr. Grace's, set apart for that purpose, a proposition was made by me, that, since our books were often referr'd to in our disquisitions upon the queries, it might be convenient to us to have them altogether where we met, that upon occasion they might be consulted; and by thus clubbing our books to a common library, we would, while we lik'd to keep them together, have each of us the advantage of using the books of all the other members, which would be nearly as beneficial as if each owned the whole. It was lik'd and agreed to . . .

Upon this simple logic, with which in 1728 Benjamin Franklin (as he relates in the *Autobiography*) persuaded his fellow-members of the Junto to pool their books, rests the existence of the library as an institution. It has never been possible for users of books, as individuals, to acquire and own all the books of which they may have need; but in "clubbing [their] books to a common library" they have fashioned a device by which they may extend their individual resources almost indefinitely. "Clubbing" of books occurs, in consequence, at every level of organization—the village, the county, the municipality, the state or province, and the nation; the local and the national association; the university and the inter-university center. There are even beginnings of international libraries.

While the function of the individual library is, in consequence, to give its readers access to as extensive a collection of books as the local circumstances require and permit, the function of the library system as a whole may be said, by extension, to be that of providing the inquirer with access to any book of which he may need, no matter how rare or how ephemeral, no matter when or where published.

In response to their usefulness, libraries have multiplied enormously in number and increased fantastically in size. Yet in spite of these enormous resources in number and size of collections, libraries too frequently fail to satisfy their users. The reasons are close at hand.

In the first place, the diversity of books is so great that no single library, no matter how ample its book-fund, can possess them all. In consequence, libraries in a number of countries have developed cooperative arrangements for sharing the burdens of acquisition in an attempt to assure that the diversity of demand will be met; but the quantity of publication is so vast that even such arrangements can hope to make possible only a selection from the total.

Quantity of publication has its effect, in addition, on the record of what is published and what is acquired. For some purposes this record is deficient in completeness, in timeliness, or in degree of analysis; for other purposes, the very attempt to make it complete renders it turgid and congested, tending to hide rather than to reveal the needed and useful work.

Furthermore, although libraries have also developed various mechanisms for making their joint resources available to all inquirers, even in many cases across national boundaries and between continents, yet the obstacles to such service are very great, and the techniques for overcoming them very imperfect. Quite apart from inherent obstacles and faulty technique, it is necessarily the case that the first responsibility of an individual library is to its local constituency; any assistance to the inquirer at a distance must inevitably defer to the local needs, and under present conditions is given, furthermore, as a courtesy rather than as of right.

All of these are deficiencies of the system as a whole. To these must be added, in the case of any particular inquiry, the deficiencies of the local library which is the inquirer's first recourse—deficiencies of content, organization, or facilities for service, or of the arrangements by which it can call upon resources beyond its own.

The cumulative effect of all these deficiencies is to interpose to a large proportion of all inquiries which seek to make use of library resources a series of crippling frustrations resulting either from the inadequacy of the library of first resort, or from the difficulties of learning what recorded sources of information exist elsewhere and where they may be found, or from the obstacles to procuring them, even after they have been identified, whether by loan or by purchase of copies or photocopies. The effect of such frustrations is to create, in total, a staggering obstacle to the thoroughness and effective-

ness — or even the commencement — of inquiry. In the light of the great services of which books are capable, if only they are accessible when needed, the loss to society and to the individual which results from these obstacles to their accessibility is incalculable.

The belief that these defects might be corrected through improved techniques or superior organization led the Ford Foundation to seek the assistance of the Folger Shakespeare Library in convoking during the early months of 1955 two meetings, representative of users of libraries, administrators of organizations containing libraries, and librarians, to consider steps to be taken. This group freely explored various approaches to the problems of libraries, and many suggestions resulted: for acquiring fuller knowledge of library resources now available and for using this knowledge to coordinate the acquisitions programs of libraries; for planning programs of preservation of deteriorating materials and of relocating little-used materials so as to assure maximum accessibility and usefulness; and for the development and exploitation of scientific aids to learning. Perhaps the central conclusion of the discussion was that libraries, though suffering from all the effects of the machine age, have gained disproportionately little benefit from it; that because libraries do not provide a market large enough to stimulate the supply of special equipment for their peculiar needs, many potentially applicable developments in science and technology have not been brought to library tasks. At its second meeting the group unanimously recommended the establishment of a planning body, completely independent of other organizations and free to devote itself to an attack upon the various problems of libraries.

Subsequent action by the Ford Foundation, embodying the essentials of the recommendations of the Folger Library Conferences, resulted in the establishment of the Council on Library Resources in September 1956 with the aid of a grant of five million dollars from the Foundation to enable it to undertake a five-year program with the objective of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular. The year just concluded marks the fifth year of the program.

At this point it is appropriate to attempt, in a brief space, to summarize the Council's experience during its first five years.

During the period there were available to the Council sums totalling \$5,168,851, representing payments on the Ford Foundation's grant plus interest. Obligations during the period amounted to \$4,524,951, of which \$602,854 constituted administrative expenses and \$3,922,097 appropriations for the substantive program. Although an unobligated balance of \$643,900 was carried over into the present year, this balance was completely earmarked for projects already authorized by the Council.

**GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS,
SEPTEMBER 1956 - JUNE 1961**

Fiscal Year	Grants		Contracts		Council Admin- istered Projects		Total Appropriations	
	No.	Amount	No.	Amount	No.	Amount	No.	Amount
1957	4	\$ 192,400	—	—	—	—	4	\$ 192,400
1958	18	313,970	11	\$ 85,146	3	\$ 4,245	32	403,361
1959	24	952,705	10	306,201	5	16,916	39	1,275,822
1960	26	429,534	8	118,177	4	21,500	38	569,211
1961	35	947,803	20	599,840	4	9,650	59	1,557,293
Totals	107	\$2,836,412	49	\$1,109,364	16	\$52,311	172	\$3,998,087
Adjustments (refunds)								75,990
Total Appropriations (net)							172	\$3,922,097

The appropriations for the substantive program were, as shown by the preceding table, 172 in number, distributed as grants, contracts and Council-administered projects. Grants accounted for 71% of the dollar-value of the appropriations, contracts for 28% and Council-administered projects for 1%. The majority (102) of appropriations were less than \$10,000 each; an additional 32 were less than \$25,000; another 10 less than \$50,000; and still another 18 less than \$100,000. Ten appropriations were of \$100,000 or more, and four of these were of \$200,000 or more.

The projects which constitute the Council's substantive program have been listed and described year by year in the *Annual Reports* and with few exceptions have been announced in greater detail at the time of their inception or conclusion in the Council's *Recent Developments* series.

Because of their wide diversity of subject matter, it is difficult to derive, from a mere listing of these projects, a

sense of unity or systematic approach in the program as a whole. For this reason it has seemed worth while to list them in the classified arrangement, by topic of investigation, which appears as Appendix A. It is hoped that a listing in this form may provide a sense of the pattern of intention which underlies the program, the relevance of individual projects to the whole, and the degree to which development has been consecutive, building from one project to the next. The listing in Appendix A identifies 155 project titles, reduced from the larger number of appropriations by consolidation where several appropriations were made for the same or similar projects. Appendix A also lists, where appropriate, reports or other publications resulting from projects.

Sixty-three of these projects, or 41% of the total, are recorded in the list as being still "in progress" at the end of the period. This means that a large proportion of the Council's undertakings, including some of the most important, even though begun early in its career, have not yet come to fruition. In other cases, even though a series of projects may be marked as "completed," the problems concerned may still be unresolved. An example of this may be found under the rubric of development of devices for individual use of microtext. Although five projects in this series have been "completed," two still "in progress" carry on the inquiry.

In spite of the fact that so large a proportion of projects is still incomplete, it is nevertheless possible to identify some important progress toward the goals envisioned by the group that met at the Folger Library in 1955.

Under the heading of coordination of resources may be mentioned the assistance given to the extension of the Farmington Plan for the Cooperative Acquisition of Foreign Publications, in the effort more nearly to reach its objective of assuring that at least one copy of every foreign publication of potential research value be available in the United States. Under this heading, too, fall such projects as the production of the third edition of the *Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada* and the placing of the record of serial holdings of American libraries on a continuing basis; and the realization of a 75-year-old dream through the creation of the National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections; the preparation of a guide to photographed materials for historical research in American repositories and the initiation

of plans for systematically improving the national resources for research through photocopying projects.

Under the heading of preservation, the Council has assisted in making known, with exactitude and for the first time, just what has happened, is happening, and will happen with respect to the deterioration of book paper. More than that, these studies have produced a formula which makes possible, within economic feasibilities, the production of book paper possessing characteristics of durability and permanence equal to the best book papers of the past. This preventive of future deterioration has, with little promotion on the Council's part, already gained considerable commercial acceptance, and will undoubtedly gain more with the promotion being planned.

This accomplishment looks principally to the prevention of problems of preservation in the future. What about the vast quantities of deteriorating materials already held by libraries? Here the Council's undertakings have identified potentially applicable procedures (such as aerosol deacidification) which, however, have not as yet been brought to technological or economic feasibility. Meanwhile, preservation through microcopying is an accepted method, limited in application only by cost. Several of the Council's completed projects (such as the AVCO Corporation's high-density photographic store) extend the prospect that it may become economically possible to extend miniaturization, by photography or other techniques, to problems of preservation simultaneously with those of storage and distribution.

Other completed projects under the head of preservation have to do with improved methods of binding and book repair. These have as yet made only beginnings, from which important results are expected.

A number of projects have attempted to improve the conditions of library work by coordination of effort. Such coordination requires standardization of practice as a prerequisite. Accordingly, under this head fall such projects as those related to the development of uniform practices in cataloging and book-classification, the international coordination of the principles of cataloging, the organization of the bibliographic record and the physical handling of the microforms, the support of a cooperative enterprise for the processing of books (the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.) and the pro-

motion of "cataloging in source." Measurable results have derived from all of these.

The relocation of the vast masses of little-used materials in libraries so as better to realize their potential value was one of the desiderata of the Folger Library Conference. Toward this objective the Council has made little headway. Relocation, in the literal sense, is indeed not likely to be achieved; what is to be sought is an arrangement by which the existence of materials, wherever they may be, is made known to those who need them, and the materials themselves made available promptly and inexpensively when wanted. The elements of such arrangements already exist, but they must be greatly improved. Here again, some of the Council's ventures indicate that means for improvement may be found through photographic (or other) miniaturizing and microstorage of the little-used materials, and through perfected techniques of copying and transmission which will make the contents of these microstores widely available.

Libraries exist by virtue of copying, and it may be asserted that they exist for the purpose of making copying possible. For this reason, the Council's program has placed much emphasis on developing the applications of copying techniques to library work. But copying involves not only technical but also legal considerations. An important study was concluded just before the end of the period resulting in the adoption, by four of the library associations, of a statement of principle regarding photocopying in libraries.

Finally, under the head of scientific aids to learning, the Council's projects evidence more commencements than completions. Into this category fall attempts to provide the scholar with devices which will make it possible for him conveniently to make and use the least expensive and in some respects the most convenient form of transcript of library materials, namely, microcopy; but these attempts are hitherto unproductive. Significantly productive, by contrast, have been the applications of mechanical devices to the techniques of bibliographic compilation and publication in the *Index Medicus* project of the National Library of Medicine. The various testing and standardizing projects of the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association (including its study of book-charging systems) have also proved useful. A number of investigations into the possibilities of applying the

computer-type devices to library tasks, such as cataloging, indexing and text-searching, have produced interesting results which show the machines superior in accuracy, speed and tirelessness to human beings, but have not as yet proved that they can economically replace human effort for these purposes.

Having estimated the progress of the program thus far, the Trustees of the Ford Foundation made the decision, in December 1960, to enable the Council to continue, for a new seven-to-ten year period, its programs of development and demonstration. At the same time the Foundation stipulated that the Council segregate, so as to give concentrated attention to them, those portions of its program looking to the development of methods for the mechanization of the operations of information storage and retrieval in libraries. The Council is well prepared to do this, since a number of projects completed or under way will contribute to such a concentrated effort. Among these are the inquiries into high-density photographic storage, the studies of machine indexing and retrieval, and the investigations (at the University of Illinois and the Library of Congress) seeking situations in which mathematics, psychology, mechanics and electronics can render library work more efficient. During the major part of the past year a special committee of the Council has been laying the plans for a concentrated study which will be initiated during the present year.

The experience of the Council during the past five years proves, if any proof were necessary, that the problems of libraries are entrenched, have already resisted many energetic and intelligent attacks, and do not now yield to the first blow; but neither are the problems ineluctable. With some accomplishment and an even larger amount of promising commencement behind it, the Council enters its second period with confidence and most interested expectation.

The projects commenced and completed with the Council's assistance during the year just past are the subjects of the following chapters.

Verner W. Clapp
President

NEW PROJECTS

During the past year the Council appropriated \$1,557,293 for 59 projects, of which seven were extensions or renewals of prior undertakings. The new projects are described briefly below in the four categorizations which have been found useful for such presentations in previous reports.

Improvement of the Means of Bibliographic Access

(These means include the devices, arrangements and forms of organization through which the existence of a source of recorded information is known, together with the location from which it may be procured or at which it may be consulted. Examples are national bibliographies, publishers' and booksellers' lists, bibliographies, indexes, abstracting services, library catalogs, union catalogs and union lists; the techniques and mechanisms by which these are effected; bibliographic and reference service.) Sixteen projects during the past year fell in this category.

Indexing by Computer and Otherwise. A previous report has described the interesting results of the inquiry conducted by Dr. Don R. Swanson of the Ramo Wooldridge company into the possibilities of mechanical indexing, summed up in the conclusion that "though machines may never enjoy more than partial success in library indexing, a small suspicion might justifiably be entertained that people are even less promising."¹ The Council has contracted with Ramo Wooldridge for a further step in the inquiry. This will consist of an examination of the results of the first experiment to ascertain the reasons for success or failure, both by the machines and the human indexers; and the search procedure will be modified accordingly.

The Council has also supported another inquiry in the same area of investigation, but dealing with the literature of the law. Mr. John F. Harty, Director of the Health Law Center of the University of Pittsburgh, has had some success in legal literature searching with the aid of computers, and partici-

¹ IV: 23-24. (Citations in this form are to the Council's annual reports; in this instance to its *Fourth Annual Report*, pages 23-24.)

pated in a demonstration of electronic searching during the meetings of the American Bar Association in Washington in August 1960. A grant from the Council will enable him to prepare the entire text of the legal codes of New York, New Jersey and Pennsylvania for computer processing, and to conduct parallel searches both by these machines and by traditional methods so as to compare the results in terms of adequacy of search, speed and cost.

Also in the field of law, the Council has supported an experiment to test the merits of "coordinate indexing" as the basis for searching legal literature.²

It is thought that this method may provide greater depth of analysis, with resultant greater accuracy in searching, and with advantages of both speed and cost over the traditional methods of indexing. Under the title "Project Lawsearch," three law publishers (Matthew Bender and Company, Bureau of National Affairs, and the Michie Company) have joined to index by this method a body of material on the subject of motor carriers.

However, "coordinate indexing" requires special equipment for matching the indexing terms in desired combinations in the process of conducting a search. This can be performed by computers; but because it seems important that a legal searching system be under the control of the inquirer, the Council has contracted with Jonker Business Machines, Inc. for the development of a simple device, based on its Termatrex equipment, for cheaply disseminating the results of the indexing and for enabling any individual to conduct searches with its use.

Catalogs and Cataloging. A number of grants and contracts were concerned with the improvement of the library catalog. Assistance was given to the American Library Association to continue the studies looking to the revision of the *ALA Catalog Code* and to reprint the code for *Cataloging of Persian Works*,

² "Coordinate indexing" involves indexing by single concepts rather than by phrases or by words subordinated to each other in a classified pattern as in traditional systems. Thus, a treatise on the indexing of legal literature would be indexed under the headings "indexing," "law" and "literature." A treatise on the indexing of medical literature would similarly be indexed by "indexing," "medicine," "literature." A search under either "indexing" or "literature" or a combination of these would discover both treatises; while the use of any three of the terms would narrow the search down to one of the two treatises.

resulting from a grant made in 1957 to Dr. Nasser Sharify, and already out of print. But the concentration of projects were with respect to the physical production and form of the card catalog.

Because of the severity of the use to which they are typically put, catalog cards are generally made of expensive all-rag stock. Following the success of Mr. William J. Barrow's investigation into the production of a permanent/durable book-paper from chemical wood pulp, the Council made it possible for the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association to commission him to undertake a study with a view to improving and standardizing the physical characteristics of catalog cards, and possibly also to reducing the cost. A report of this study, which has already beneficially affected commercial production, is in press.

The reasons for and the nature of the Council's efforts to improve the means for preparing cards for the catalog with the aid of a "cataloger's camera" have been described in an earlier report.³ The camera worked, but its product could not meet the standards established by the printed catalog card. During the past year the Council returned to the problem in three projects. In one, the Library Technology Project undertook a study of the comparative costs of producing catalog cards by various methods; because of the many variables involved, these facts have never been known with exactness sufficient for guiding a choice of method in particular situations. In another project the de Florez Company was commissioned to construct a stencil-process card duplicator with automatic features enabling it to produce complete sets of cards with up to six different headings from a single typing. In still a third project the Massachusetts Institute of Technology will commission the design of an electronically-controlled card-printer which will similarly produce complete sets of cards from a single keyboarding operation, and which, if successful, is estimated to be able to save the time of one cataloger and two typists in the M.I.T. Library alone.

Book-Marking. Two small grants to the American Library Association were intended to assist to successful completion the improvements in this field under development by the Library Technology Project since 1959. One was for further

³ II: 14-15.

BOOK-LABELING — This typewriter has especially designed features for printing “call numbers” on labels for backstrips of library books. The machine, developed by Battelle Memorial Institute under Library Technology Project sponsorship, is receiving field tests.

work on a book-label printing device; the other for an investigation of adhesives suitable for book-labeling. Because of the great variations in book-cover stock, no single satisfactory adhesive is at present available.

Cooperative Book-Processing. Earlier reports have recorded the Council’s interest in the cooperative book-processing center established by a number of small public libraries of independent jurisdictions as the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. At the end of its first year a study of this center’s operations was conducted by Mrs. Brigitte L. Kenney and was published by the American Library Association in 1959 under the title *Cooperative Centralized Processing*. The interest created by this report justified repetition of the review after a longer period of development of the center. Consequently, under a grant to the Association a new report is being prepared by Mrs. Frances D. Carhart of the Des Moines Public Library.

Bibliographies. The Council gave support during the year to several bibliographical enterprises: through the American Library Association to the preparation of a supplement for the years 1950-1960 to Robert B. Downs' *Resources of American Libraries*; through the International Association of Music Libraries to work on the *International Inventory of Musical Sources*; through the Purdue Research Foundation to the publication and distribution of the fourth volume of *Masters' Theses in the Pure and Applied Sciences* (this was done to assure the continuity of the series pending a decision of the American library world, later taken in the affirmative, whether to support an annual record of this kind); and to the Johns Hopkins University for interim support to *Economics Library Selections* (this likewise was to assure continuity, pending receipt of other support, of a service which the Council regards as having an important potential contribution to an ultimate general book-selection service for college-university libraries).

Improvement of the Means of Physical Access

(These means include the devices, arrangements and forms of organization through which a source of recorded information, once identified and its location known, is put into an inquirer's hands. Examples are the procedures of distribution and acquisition, book storage and preservation, inter-library lending and photocopying.) Under this category the Council assisted 25 projects during the past year.

Acquisition. Two on-going projects of the Council are attempting to improve the arrangements by which materials for scholarly research are made more widely available through photocopy. The first of these is the preparation, by the American Historical Society, of a guide to photocopied resources for historical research in the United States and Canada. The second is the study, under the auspices of the American Council of Learned Societies, of the possibility of drafting a general plan for the photocopying of scholarly materials. In continuation of these inquiries, but in a narrower field — that of American history — the Council assisted the Library of Congress to convene in April 1961 a group to coordinate plans for photocopying in European repositories.⁴

⁴ Appendix A, item 52.

Preservation — Improved Bookpaper. In September 1960 a group of librarians and archivists, book publishers, book manufacturers and papermakers met in Washington under the joint auspices of the American Library Association and the Virginia State Library to discuss the results of the Virginia State Library-William J. Barrow investigations in developing specifications and a formula for producing a permanent/durable book-paper competitive with available book-papers.⁵ The discussion was most encouraging for the prospect of wider adoption of such papers, and the group voted unanimously to invite the American Library Association to establish a representative group for the continuing discussion of the subject and the search for acceptable solutions to the various problems. The proceedings of the meeting have been published by the Virginia State Library, and the American Library Association is preparing to adopt the recommendation.

Bookbinding. The American Library Association took a preliminary step last year toward the development of performance standards for library binding by sending a survey team, consisting of a librarian, a library binder and a testing expert to visit libraries across the country in order to categorize the types of binding needed in libraries and to lay the plans for a testing-standardizing program. The report of the survey has been published by the Association and is expected to lead directly to the next step.⁶

The type of binding called variously “perfect,” “adhesive” or “unsewn” (in which the pages are held together by adhesive) would seem to offer many advantages for library equally with edition binding, but assurance of the longevity of such bindings is insufficient to win confidence for their application to library work. During the past year the Council contracted with Mr. William J. Barrow for a preliminary investigation of the possibility of tests for providing such assurance. The results of his inquiry have been published and a testing program will be undertaken during the present year.⁷

The Council also took advantage of the European visit of Mr. Fred W. Alpers, a member of a Cleveland firm of library bookbinders, to secure a report on developments in library

⁵ IV: 27-29. Also: Appendix A, items 60-63.

⁶ Appendix A, item 67.

⁷ Appendix A, item 69.

binderies abroad. His report, though of interest, did not find in European experience suggestions for improvement applicable to the situation of American libraries.⁸

Fire Protection and Insurance. A series of tests conducted several years ago by a fire insurance company in cooperation with the New York Public Library called attention to the unsuspectedly great hazard from fire associated with a certain type of bookstack. Although this type of stack is no longer used in new construction, the tests had important potential consequences for libraries through stiffened requirements for protective devices and in increased costs of insurance. It became obvious that a more general inquiry was needed immediately. At the request of the Association of Research Libraries the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association has commissioned a study from Gage-Babcock Associates, Inc. This study will review the actual fire risk experience of libraries over the years, will make recommendations for building and storage-space criteria to achieve minimum fire, explosion or windstorm hazard both in new buildings and reconstruction, will develop a model insurance contract and encourage favorable ratings and loss-adjustment procedure, and draft a manual for library use. An advisory committee has been appointed to assist the study.

A National Plan for Preservation of Deteriorating Materials. Although the general adoption of an improved book-paper may in the future gradually reduce the deterioration problem for libraries of record, this problem is very much with them at the present time. Some libraries (notably the New York Public Library and the Library of Congress) are expending increasingly large proportions of their total book funds for microfilming materials of short life-expectancy. A national plan for sharing this burden is a growing necessity, and the Association of Research Libraries has appointed a committee to take steps toward such a plan. To estimate the size of the problem in terms of the number of books involved and their rate of deterioration seemed to the committee to be a first need. To assist in reaching such an estimate, the Council commissioned from Mr. Randolph W. Church, the State Librarian of Virginia, a design for a sampling procedure. Later, the Council made it possible for the committee to secure the services of a firm of statisticians to execute the plan.

⁸ Appendix A, item 68.

Meanwhile, various other investigations aided by the Council, especially those in the area of microcopying mentioned below, may be expected to contribute to the solution of the deterioration problem.

Storage. The Council renewed the grant to the Yale University Library for the support of its program for developing and demonstrating the basis, operation and results of a Selective Book Retirement Program.⁹

Copying. The past five years have witnessed the coming of age of the office copying devices, and they have found ample scope for employment in libraries, even though they are in general designed for reproducing separate sheets rather than pages in bound books. In order to assemble, organize and evaluate information regarding these devices so as to furnish a basis of choice among them for library applications, the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association has commissioned a study from Mr. William R. Hawken of Berkeley, California. Meanwhile, too, the Council has contracted with the de Florez Company for the prototype of a book-cradle which may be able to increase the usefulness of the office copying devices for library work.

⁹ III: 33.

BOOK-COPYING — This automatic book-cradle/page-turner, with a built-in copying camera, was built by the de Florez Company with the intent to facilitate copying from books. The model is now being tested.

HIGH REDUCTION MICROCOPYING — This optical bench is being used in conjunction with the study, at Intectron Incorporated, of various factors involved in photocopying at high ratios of reduction. More information is needed about various aspects of high reduction microphotography.

Microcopying. Although photocopying at high ratios of reduction offers advantages for dissemination (by making it possible, for example, to reproduce 10,000 pages at the cost of one), the technical problems are severe. More information is needed regarding the relationships between light, lens, emulsion, film base, and the other components of a high-reduction system. An investigation looking to the development of such information, to be so presented as to assist a microphotographer in making a best choice of components to achieve a desired result, has been undertaken for the Council by Intectron, Inc. of Boston, Massachusetts.

In the field of standardization of microfilming practice, the Council has assisted the American Library Association's Committee on Library Standards for Microfilming to prepare a new edition of the *Guide to Microfilming Practice*.

One of the most obvious advantages to be obtained by libraries from microcopying is in saving of storage space, but the cost of microcopying is so great as rarely to justify its use for space-saving alone. Additional justification is required, such as saving of binding costs, preservation against deterioration, ease of duplication, or adaptation to mechanized duplicating or information storage-and-retrieval devices.

During the year the Council has initiated studies on several aspects of the problem. It has commissioned a study from Messrs. Forbes and Waite of Waltham, Massachusetts, of the technological and economic factors involved in miniaturizing a collection of 100,000 bound volumes of periodicals, with a view to ascertaining whether the costs of microcopying can be so reduced by various devices as to give it an economic advantage in storage cost over the retention of the originals. The Council has also arranged with the AVCO Corporation for the addition of hard-copy read-out, based upon the Printapix tube (a cathode ray tube capable of producing through electrostatic printing a facsimile of stored information) to the high-density store previously described.¹⁰ In addition, the National Bureau of Standards is preparing for the Council a state-of-the-art review, publication of which is expected, of information storage and retrieval devices making use of photofacsimile storage.

The Council has also attempted to promote the development of devices for library use in producing microcopies. One such device is a step-and-repeat camera for making microcards or microfiches by an inexpensive, dry and immediate process.

¹⁰ IV: 29-30.

TOWARD GREATER PLEASURE IN READING MICROFILM— Various factors affecting the reading of microfilm images are being investigated with the aid of this apparatus especially constructed for the purpose by the Battelle Memorial Institute. Especial note is made of "typical" reader reactions.

Another device, the "scholar's camera," is intended to produce fully processed 35 mm. microfilm within a few minutes of copying. Both devices are being engineered by the Bell and Howell Company.

The Council has continued its search, previously reported at some length, for devices to increase the contribution of the microforms to individual research by freeing their use from dependence upon the institutionalized reading machine.¹¹ In one inquiry the John R. Miles Company has continued work on a 10x-30x variable microscope magnifier for reading microtext; in another, the Battelle Memorial Institute is conducting an investigation of the factors affecting reader satisfaction in the use of microcopy, with a view to developing more satisfactory devices.

Communication of Information. One of the Council's earliest grants made possible a demonstration of the use of closed-circuit television between the central and branch libraries of a university.¹² The results were, for several reasons, not such as to justify general adoption of the idea. Nevertheless, it would appear that the techniques of telecommunication should be able to contribute to the efficiency of library work by widening the geographic service area of individual libraries and, in the process, by reducing the required number of collections of specialized or little-used material. The Council has consequently hoped that continuing development in the arts of graphic communication might at some stage make these contributions feasible. In order to evaluate the present state of these arts for the purpose, a survey of available techniques, equipment and channels for telefacsimile applicable to a library installation is being made by Image Instruments, Inc. of Boston, Massachusetts.

Electronic applications find their place, too, in systems for providing reading matter for the blind. The Council is supporting a project, conducted in part by the Library of Congress and in part by Recording for the Blind, Inc. of New York, for testing the effectiveness of tape recordings of "talking books," so encapsulated as to make them simple for a blind reader to use, in comparison with the heavier and more cumbersome disk recordings now used for the purpose.

¹¹ IV: 31-37.

¹² I: 22-23.

Display. Finally, under the head of improvement of the means of physical access, may be mentioned the project of the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association for the design of an improved newspaper stick to make possible the display of newspapers with the expenditure of less manpower than present sticks require.

Improvement of the Administrative Bases of Library Work

(Under this head are included those arrangements which bring the means of bibliographic and of physical access to the service of the inquirer. Examples are the planning of library buildings, library administration and finance, training of staff, and interlibrary cooperation.) Eleven projects fell in this category.

Administration of Small Public Libraries. It has for some time been recognized that efficient public library service, resting upon collections of adequate size and diversity to be able to provide the variety of services demanded by present-day conditions, requires a much broader basis both in terms of the population served and in sources of financial support than did the typical village or small town library of the past. Current trends are therefore toward the consolidation of library units so as to serve metropolitan, county, or even multi-county areas. Meanwhile, however, there are still many thousands of village and small town libraries, whose operating personnel and governing boards are largely deprived of the benefits of professional discussion and publication to which the staffs of the larger libraries have routine access. To give these small libraries the benefit of information regarding the best practice in the various areas of their operation — book-selection, processing, service, building management, exhibits, selection of personnel, work-simplification, community relations, questions of censorship, etc. — the American Library Association has initiated a Small Libraries Project, the aim of which is to prepare a looseleaf manual composed of a series of pamphlets, addressed to the boards of trustees as well as to the librarians of small public libraries, on the various aspects of small library management. The project is being conducted in cooperation with the state library agencies which will participate in defraying the costs of distribution and which can take advantage of

the project by including in the manual, as appropriate, material of state interest.

Demonstrations of Library Service. The American Library Association has not participated in any international exposition since 1915. Last year the Association was invited to take part in the Century 21 International Exposition to be held in Seattle in 1962, with emphasis on the applications of science and technology to modern living. This seemed to offer an opportunity not only to emphasize the contribution of libraries to modern society, but especially for developing, with the aid of organizations concerned with data processing mechanisms and with information storage-and-retrieval devices, some exhibits which might presage the manner in which science and technology may be applied to library operations in the future. It was thought, besides, that the very development of such exhibits might accelerate the coming into being of the developments which they would illustrate. The Council has, in consequence, assisted the Association in developing a plan for such an exhibit.

Standards for Library Service. The Association of School Librarians of the American Library Association has, in cooperation with a number of other national educational and library groups, developed a statement of minimum *Standards for School Library Programs 1960*. However, it is the Association's experience that such standards do not obtain acceptance merely through publication. The Council has lent assistance to an effort at implementation through promotion of knowledge of the standards among educational, lay and library groups, and through the preparation of informational material for this purpose.

Testing and Standardizing. The Library Technology Project of the American Library Association came into being, with a grant from the Council assuring its support for two years, on May 1, 1959.¹³ An advisory committee was simultaneously formed to guide its development. Already at the end of its first year the Project was able to show useful accomplishment in bringing together existing standards and specifications and the results of existing testing programs of potential usefulness to libraries, in making these available, and in initiating new testing and developmental programs. The details of these are recorded in its own annual report and in the column

¹³ II: 29-31; III: 38-39; IV: 20-21.

which it publishes in the *ALA Bulletin*. Encouraged by this success, the Council has entrusted a number of investigations to the Project's care, several of which are mentioned in this report.

Prior to renewing the grant for the Project during the past year, the Council commissioned, through the firm of Sidney Hollander Associates, of Baltimore, a survey to ascertain the degree to which the Project's activity is being directed to the need, and its effectiveness in meeting it. The report was reassuring on both counts.

Although the Project is sponsored by one national library association, it is not intended that its benefits should be restricted to the members of a single group. Consequently, under the new grant measures will be taken to secure representation on the Project's governing board of at least one other major group (the Special Libraries Association), and to make the Project's findings more readily accessible to the members of that and other groups also.

Equipment. To bring the producers and consumers together on the development of standards for the special equipment and supplies used by libraries, the Library Technology Project has sponsored the formation of a special sectional committee of the American Standards Association. One of the committee's projects concerns standards for wood furniture for library use—a form of equipment for which libraries spend large sums without adequate specifications, resulting on occasion in costly disappointments. For such standards physical tests are needed. A small grant has enabled the committee to develop tests for the purpose.

Improvement of Records Systems. Further support was given to the study of book-circulation systems conducted by George Fry and Associates of Chicago under the guidance of an advisory committee of the American Library Association, including provision for the construction of the working model of a simple borrower-participation book-charging device. Assistance was also given to Mr. Ralph Blasingame, Jr., the State Librarian of Pennsylvania, to enable him to investigate the application of punched card data processing mechanisms to selected library operations (not including the financial and personnel operations which libraries share with other agencies and where the performance of such machines is comparatively well known). The purpose is to secure cost data

on such applications, as contrasted with traditional methods. No satisfactory presentation of such data is now available.

Planning

Seven grants and contracts fell under this head. Of these, several were to make possible meetings, dealing with the functions of state libraries, or of the program of the Council of National Library Associations, or the problems of providing library service in metropolitan areas. Two major projects had to do with the possibilities of mechanization (automation) in libraries.

Mechanization in Libraries. The Library of the Chicago Undergraduate Division of the University of Illinois expects in the near future to be required to give, in a new building on a new campus, an enormously increased service to a much larger university population. To prepare itself for this increased responsibility the Library decided to investigate the possibilities of achieving greater efficiency through mechanization, and, as a preliminary step, has flow-charted its entire operation in machine (i.e. computer) terms. The Council has made a grant to enable the Library to engage an engineering firm, specializing in computer and other data processing systems, to examine the operations thus analyzed with a view to identifying those to which mechanization may profitably be applied. It is hoped that this study may establish certain principles applicable to university libraries generally.

The situation of the Library of Congress is similar to that of the Library of the Chicago Undergraduate Division, but more acute. Although this library has over the years sought and employed mechanisms in many of its operations, these have been piecemeal applications. The computer-type data processing machines offer promise of advantages from a more systematic, overall approach. Several attempts to secure such an approach from surveys by engineering firms have resulted only in recommendations for more piecemeal tinkering. The Library finally decided to secure a survey by a group of acknowledged experts in the applications of computers, mathematics, operations research and human engineering to data processing systems. It is hoped that from this may come a plan for bringing the advantages of mechanization systematically to the operations of research libraries.

PROJECTS COMPLETED

A number of projects supported by the Council were completed during the past year. In cases in which the project was initiated during the year, or in which its completion led to renewal or to a succeeding project, note has been made of this in the preceding chapter. In other cases, also, a record of the completion of the project, with the citation of any report or publication resulting from it, may be found in Appendix A. The following list is in consequence not inclusive, but mentions some additional completions of greatest interest.

Mechanization of Bibliographic Operations. By the end of 1959 the National Library of Medicine completed the project for converting the *Current List of Medical Literature* to the *Index Medicus*, making use of an integrated series of mechanisms for the production of the new publication, including tape-operated typewriters, punched card sorting machines and automatic cameras for creating the printer's copy.¹⁴ The details of the new program, recorded in a separately published appendix to the *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association* for January 1961, described an impressively successful project with respect to improved format, ease of consultation, and expedited production. In terms of making possible the hoped-for retrieval of information for sub-disciplines of medicine the project was unsuccessful, and the Library is already seeking new solutions.

The Library Technology Project's attempt to develop an improved card platen for typewriters which might facilitate the production of catalog cards resulted in a device too complicated for its purpose. Another attempt will be made.

Bibliographical Standardization. The inquiry by Mr. Gustave A. Harrer of Boston University and Mr. Alex Ladenson of the Chicago Public Library into the possibility of putting the machine-coding business practices of book publishers to use for the book-selection and book-purchasing activities of libraries has been completed and published.¹⁵ Although no immediate results will follow (because publishers will not adopt machine-processing for inventory control and invoicing as soon as was earlier expected), the study is on file to show

¹⁴ II: 12-13. Also, Appendix A, item 22.

¹⁵ IV: 15. Also, Appendix A, item 12.

how such processing may be done most usefully, if and when it is undertaken.

The investigation by Professor Wesley Simonton of the University of Minnesota, under the auspices of the Association of Research Libraries, on the bibliographical control of the microforms has also been completed, and a report has ensued.¹⁶ The Association has appointed a committee to implement the recommendations of the report, and results may be expected, effecting improved cataloging of the microforms and the registration of microcopying projects.

Acquisition. The study of barriers to the international flow of books in the Americas, undertaken for the Pan American Union by Mr. Peter Jennison of New York University and Mr. William H. Kurth of the National Library of Medicine as a working paper for the 11th Inter-American Conference has been completed and published under the title *Books in the Americas*, with an accompanying Spanish version.¹⁷ It still awaits the official consideration for which it was prepared.

By contrast, the report on the status of arrangements for the procurement of foreign publications under the provisions of the Agricultural Trade Development Assistance Act of 1954 as amended (Public Law 480), has taken its place in a sequence which has led to concrete results.¹⁸ After several false starts the program authorized by the Law is now finally under way as the result of an appropriation to the Library of Congress, with the expectation of bringing many foreign publications of research value into American libraries.

Utilization of Library Storage Space. In 1958 the Council convened a meeting to plan studies of the most efficient use of the storage space of research libraries in the face of the increasing proportions of little-used materials being acquired by such libraries. Thereafter, two studies were initiated — one, to develop the bases and to demonstrate the operation of a compact storage program, and the other, under the auspices of the University of Chicago Library, to seek patterns in the use of research library materials which might provide criteria for assigning priorities in claims on space to various categories of material.¹⁹

¹⁶ IV: 15. Also, Appendix A, item 30.

¹⁷ IV: 22. Also, Appendix A, items 53, 54.

¹⁸ IV: 16. Also, Appendix A, item 56.

¹⁹ III: 32-33. Also, Appendix A, item 59.

The University of Chicago has now reported in a careful study by Dr. Herman H. Fussler, the Director of its Library, and Dr. Julian L. Simon, entitled *Patterns in the Use of Books in Large Research Libraries*. This work provides the bases for predicting with some assurance the future rate of use of books if certain facts regarding their past history are known. Because of the technical nature of the report, a summary is in preparation. Practical applications of its findings will be awaited with interest.

Copying—Legal Problems. The assistance given by the Council to the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying has been previously reported.²⁰ During the past year the Committee came to a conclusion on its primary assignment—copying of published materials.

Copying in libraries involves legal problems relating to copyright and the interpretative doctrine of “fair use.” So long as copying was done by hand, by typewriter, or even by full-scale photography, these problems were not severe. With the coming of microfilming a clearer understanding was needed as to what constitutes “fair use.” In 1935 the Joint Committee of Scientific Aids to Learning reached the so-called Gentlemen’s Agreement with the then American Book Publishers Association; but with the passage of years the Agreement has, for a number of reasons, been found defective as a guide to library practice. In 1957 the Joint Libraries Committee undertook a new study, and, with aid from the Council, retained the services of eminent legal counsel. The results of the Committee’s studies are contained in a report which was published in the official bulletins of two of the principal library associations toward the end of the year and has been approved by the four national associations represented on the Committee—the American Association of Law Libraries, the American Library Association, the Association of Research Libraries and the Special Libraries Association. The report affirms the traditional right of libraries to furnish copies of materials in their collections as a natural extension of reference service, and asserts the principle that libraries are free to provide single copies of published materials in their collections.

Regional Coordination. The survey by Dr. Keyes D. Metcalf of the possibilities of coordination among seven principal

²⁰ III: 38. Also, Appendix A, item 86.

libraries of Maine was completed and resulted in a published report.²¹

Book-Circulation Records. The arrangements by which the records of book-circulation are controlled are at one and the same time one of the most important and one of the least satisfactory aspects of library work. Though these arrangements are clerical and mechanical in nature, yet upon their efficiency depends much of a library's ability to serve. In addition, the book-charging operations are almost universally those which first present themselves to the public's view and to a considerable extent form the bottleneck of public service. Much thought and ingenuity has been expended in devising more efficient systems. Ledgers, slips and visible indicators, cards, edge-notched cards and electrical accounting machine punched cards, photographic, acoustic and thermographic recording devices — all of these have been applied in various guises and combinations to the problem; but no system has been found that is wholly satisfactory.

In 1959 the Council commissioned a preliminary inquiry with the hope of effecting some improvements in this area. In the following year a full study was undertaken by the firm of George Fry and Associates of Chicago with the guidance of an advisory committee established by the American Library Association under the chairmanship of the associate director of the Library Technology Project.²² The study, which at first included large and small public libraries and college and university libraries, was later extended to special libraries. A questionnaire was taken up and field inquiries were conducted, including careful time and cost studies of the various systems under varying conditions.

The results have now been published by the Association in a report, *Study of Circulation Control Systems*, which for the first time attempts on a broad scale to provide criteria in terms of cost for the applicability of the several systems to situations differing with respect to size of work-load, degree of borrower participation, expected or required results, and other factors. Furthermore, these data have been so organized as to provide a check list enabling a librarian to select the system most appropriate to a particular situation. The better

²¹ Appendix A, item 109.

²² IV: 20. Also, Appendix A, items 121, 122, 124.

to effect this purpose, the general report is supplemented by manuals for the use of public, college-university and special libraries.

Following the publication of the report, a series of workshops was held at the 1961 annual meetings of the national library associations under the auspices of the advisory committee and the Library Technology Project, to explain and discuss the findings.

It is believed that this study marks an important step in the identification and measurement of the elements which make for efficiency in book-circulation systems. In doing so it has also opened the way for further improvements, and work is to be continued.

Planning for Research. The past year saw the conclusion of the initial period of co-sponsorship by the Council with the National Science Foundation of the work of the National Bureau of Standards' Research information Center and Advisory Service on Information Processing.²³ This work resulted in the production of a most interesting and useful series of reports, some of the nature of "state-of-the-art" surveys, others attempting by analysis of the subject to lay the basis for future research. A list may be found at item 152 of Appendix A.

²³ III: 42-43.

APPENDIX A

PROJECTS BY SUBJECT, 1956-1961*

With Related Reports and Publications

I. *IMPROVEMENT OF THE MEANS OF BIBLIOGRAPHIC ACCESS* (i.e., of the arrangements whereby the existence of a book—or any recorded source of information—is made known)

a. *Through standardization*

i. *Cataloging rules, generally*

1. American Library Association. Assistance toward ALA Catalog Code revision project. 1960, 1961; \$8,900; in progress.
2. Nasser Sharify. Towards a cataloging code for Persian library materials. 1957, 1958; \$11,841; completed.

Nasser Sharify: *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description*. Chicago, American Library Association, 1959. xiv, 161 p. [Second printing, 1961.]

3. American Library Association. Reprint of Sharify's *Cataloging of Persian Works*. 1961; \$975; completed.

ii. *International coordination of cataloging rules*

4. American Library Association. Toward the international coordination of cataloging rules. 1957; \$1,172; completed.

Andrew D. Osborn: At a German Library Conference. *ALA Bulletin*, 51: 773-775. November 1957. [Account of the meeting of the German Library Association (Verein Deutscher Bibliothekare) in Lübeck in June 1957 by the American Library Association's representative.]

—: Zur Revision der Instruktionen für die Katalogisierung an Amerikanischen Bibliotheken: Vortrag. Gehalten auf dem Bibliothekartag in Lübeck am 13 Juni 1957. (Gekürzt) *Zeitschrift für Bibliothekswesen und Bibliographie* 4: 241-246, 1957.

5. Library of Congress. Planning of next steps toward an international cataloging code. 1957; \$314; completed.
6. International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA). For a preliminary meeting to plan an international conference on the principles of cataloging. 1958; \$16,295; completed.

* Several appropriations for the same project or for similar projects are consolidated in this listing.

International Federation of Library Associations: International Cataloging Conference, *Bulletin*, London: IFLA Working Group on Co-ordination of Cataloging Principles, 1-. November 1958-. Irregular. Processed.

IFLA International Cataloging Conference, Preliminary Meeting, London, July 19th-25th, 1959, Report. *Libri*, 9: 254-261. 1959.

International Cataloging Conference, 1961. *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries*, 14: 136. May-June 1960.

Susan M. Haskins: Moving Toward International Cataloging Agreement. *ALA Bulletin*, 54: 197-201. March 1960.

Wyllis E. Wright: International Cataloging Conference. *Library Resources and Technical Services*, 4: 85-89. Winter 1960.

7. International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA). Assistance toward an International Conference on Cataloging Principles, Paris, October 1961. 1959; \$95,420; in progress.

I.F.L.A., Organizing Committee of the International Conference on Cataloging Principles, *International Conference on Cataloging Principles Bulletin*, London, 1 (New Series)-. April 1960-. Processed.

8. American Library Association. For travel grants to promote the international coordination of cataloging rules. 1958, 1959; \$9,377; completed.
9. Music Library Association. For travel in connection with the International Conference on Cataloging Principles, Paris, October 1961. 1961; \$1,500; in progress.

iii. *Shelf-Classification of books*

10. Library of Congress. A pilot study of the use of classified book collections. 1960; \$5,525; in progress.
11. Library of Congress. Assistance toward development of a shelf-classification for law books. 1958; \$4,500; in progress.

Special Report on the Progress of the Anglo-American Law Classification Under Development by the Library of Congress. *Law Library Journal*, 52: 442-445. November 1959. Also a subsequent report in *Law Library Journal*, 53: 308-309. November 1960.

iv. *Coding of books to facilitate acquisition*

12. American Library Association. Inquiry into the feasibility of developing a numerical code for identifying and characterizing current American publications. 1960; \$4,987; completed.

G. A. Harrer and Alex Ladenson: Report on the Project to Investigate the Feasibility of a National Code Number System for Current Publications. N.p., April 1961. 25 l. Processed.

b. *Through improvement of bibliographic operations*

i. *Catalog cards and catalog card reproduction*

13. American Library Association. For testing catalog card stock. 1960; \$9,000; in progress. (Funded in part under No. 129.)
14. Radio Corporation of America. Design plan for a "cataloger's camera." 1958; \$3,000; completed.

Radio Corporation of America: Development Engineering Marketing Defense Electronic Products: *Final Report. Automatic Enlarging Instant Copy Camera*, April 6, 1959. [Camden, The Corporation, 1959.] 6 l., 4 pl. Processed.
15. Radio Corporation of America. Working model of a "cataloger's camera." 1958; \$22,789; completed.
16. American Library Association. Catalog card reproduction; a systems study, Phase I. 1961; \$49,470; in progress. (Funded under Nos. 127 and 130.)
17. The de Florez Company. Design and construction of a prototype stencil catalog card duplicator. 1960; \$16,000; in progress.
18. Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Feasibility study of the design of an automatic catalog card replicator. 1961; \$14,238; in progress.
19. American Library Association. Development of an improved card-holding device for typewriters. 1960; \$9,000; completed. (Funded under No. 129.)

ii. *Book-labeling*

20. American Library Association. Development of a book-marking system. 1959, 1960, 1961; \$43,150; in progress.
21. American Library Association. Investigation of adhesives for book-labeling. 1961; \$7,130; in progress. (Funded under No. 130.)

iii. *Compilation of bibliographies*

22. National Library of Medicine. Improvement of bibliographic compilation through mechanization, with specific application to the *Current List of Medical Literature*. 1958; \$73,800; completed.

The National Library of Medicine Index Mechanization Project. *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association*, 49: No. 1, Part 2. January 1961. 96 p.
23. American Association of Law Libraries. A mechanized compilation of a check list of legal subject headings. 1960; \$5,000; in progress.

iv. "Telereference"

24. University of Michigan, Engineering Research Institute. Feasibility study of "Telereference" (long-distance consultation of card catalogs). 1958; \$15,764; completed.

University of Michigan, Engineering Research Institute: *Final Report: Application of a Telereference System to Divisional Library Card Catalogs; A Feasibility Analysis*. [Ann Arbor, The Institute, For] Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1958. 91 p.

v. Indexing

25. Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc. Study in word correlation and automatic indexing, Phase I. 1959, 1961; \$74,556; completed.

Ramo-Wooldridge, A Division of Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.: *Word Correlation and Automatic Indexing, Phase I Final Report, "An Experiment in Automatic Text Searching," C82-OU4, Submitted to the Council on Library Resources, 30 April 1960*. Canoga Park, California, The Company, 1960. 4 v. [392 l.] Processed.

Don R. Swanson: Searching Natural Language Text by Computer. *Science*, 132: 1099-1104. October 21, 1960.

26. Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc. Study in word correlation and automatic indexing, Phase IIA. 1960; \$71,896; in progress.
27. University of Pittsburgh. Searching statutory law by computer. 1960; \$58,886; in progress.
28. Jonker Business Machines, Inc. Development of equipment for an inexpensive disseminable mechanical system for searching legal literature by "coordinate indexing" techniques, Phase I. 1961; \$41,000; in progress.
29. Matthew Bender & Co., Inc., New York; Bureau of National Affairs, Washington; The Michie Company, Charlottesville (Project Lawsearch). Experimental indexing of a body of legal literature by "coordinate indexing" techniques. 1961; \$40,000; in progress.

vi. Bibliographical control of microforms

30. Cornell University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). A study of the bibliographical control of microforms. 1960; \$11,550; completed.

Wesley Simonton: *The Bibliographical Control of Microforms, A Report Submitted to the Association of Research Libraries, June 1, 1961*. [Minneapolis, The Author, 1961.] 19 l. Processed.

c. *Through coordination of effort*

i. *Cooperative processing*

31. Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc., Springfield, Missouri. Demonstration of cooperative/centralized processing for small independent public libraries. 1957; \$4,000; completed.

Willard K. Dennis: Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. *Missouri Library Association Quarterly*, 18: 119-123. December 1957.

—: A Unique Cataloging and Processing Centre (USA). *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries*, 14: 173-174. July-August 1960.

32. American Library Association. Analysis and report on the operation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service cooperative processing center. 1958; \$795; completed.

Brigitte L. Kenney: Centralized Processing — Missouri Style. *Library Resources and Technical Services*, 2: 185-198. Summer, 1958.

—: *Cooperative Centralized Processing, A Report of the Establishment and First Year of Operation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.* Chicago, American Library Association, 1959. 98 p.

Orcena Mahoney: An Experiment in Cooperative Processing. *ALA Bulletin*, 52: 127-130. February 1958.

33. Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. For an exhibit of the Service's work at the conference of the American Library Association-Canadian Library Association, Montreal. 1960; \$163; completed.

34. American Library Association. A review and evaluation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. 1960; \$1,175; in progress.

ii. *"Cataloging in Source"*

35. Library of Congress. Preliminary investigation of the feasibility of "cataloging in source." 1958; \$2,822; completed.

Andrew D. Osborn: *Cataloging at the Source; an Opportunity for Cooperation Between the Four Major Book Arts.* Chicago, American Library Association, 1958. 18 l. Typescript.

36. Library of Congress. Demonstration of "Cataloging in Source." 1958; \$55,000; completed.

U.S. Library of Congress, Processing Department: Cataloging in Source. *Cataloging Service*, 48: 1-3, September 1958; 50: 1-4, November 1958; 53: 1-17, June 1959.

—: *The Cataloging-in-Source Experiment, A Report to The Librarian of Congress* by the Director of the Processing Department. 1960. xxiv, 199 p.

Orcena Mahoney: Cataloging in Source. *ALA Bulletin*, 54: 197-201. March 1960.

d. *Through improved bibliographic tools*

i. *Union List of Serials*

37. Joint Committee on the *Union List of Serials*. For meeting to explore next steps toward a 3d edition of the *List*. 1958; \$750; completed.
38. Joint Committee on the *Union List of Serials*, Inc. Assistance toward placing the record of serials in libraries in the United States and Canada on a continuing basis. 1959; \$244,651; in progress.

F. Bernice Field: The Program of the Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials. *Library Resources and Technical Services*, 4: 303-308. Fall 1960.

ii. *A national record of manuscript collections*

39. Library of Congress. For creation of a National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. 1958; \$200,000; in progress.

National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*, 18: 347-349. June 22, 1959.

Lee E. Grove: The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. *ALA Bulletin*, 54: 769-771. October 1960.

iii. *Guide to photofacsimiles of historical source materials*

40. American Historical Association. Preparation of a guide to the photographed historical research materials in libraries and archives in the United States and Canada. 1957; \$60,520; in progress.

Richard W. Hale, Jr.: The Guide to Photocopied Historical Materials. *National Micro News*, 42: 96-101. December 1959.

iv. *International Inventory of Musical Sources*

41. Music Library Association. Travel grant to assist U.S. participation in work on the *International Inventory of Musical Sources*. 1959; \$538; completed.
42. International Association of Music Libraries (on behalf of the International Joint Commission on the *International Inventory of Musical Sources*). For work on the *Inventory* during 1961. 1960; \$14,000; in progress.

International Musicological Society and International Association of Music Libraries — International Inventory of Musical Sources: *Recueils Imprimés XVI^e - XVII^e Siècles, Ouvrage Publié Sous la Direction De François Lesure, I, Liste Chronologique*. München-Duisburg, G. Henle, [1960]. 639 p. (Subsequent volumes: various dates and publishers.)

v. *A book-selection service for college libraries (a "New Shaw")*

43. Meeting to explore the need for and feasibility of a book-selection service for college libraries. 1959; \$4,245; completed.

Meeting to Explore Some Current and Anticipated Problems in the Building of Book Collections in College Libraries, Edgewater Beach Hotel, Chicago, Illinois, April 20-21, 1959. [Washington, Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1959] 10 1. Processed.

Report on Conference. *Library Journal*, 84: 1765-1767. June 1, 1959. (Report on the meeting of April 20-21, 1959.)

44. Johns Hopkins University. Interim assistance to *Economics Library Selections* as a book selection service for college libraries. 1960; \$2,000; completed.

Economics Library Selections, Series I: New Books in Economics. Baltimore, Department of Political Economy, The Johns Hopkins University. Published quarterly.

45. Expenses of developing a continuing book-selection service for college libraries. 1960, 1961; \$1,960; in progress.

vi. *Other bibliographies and guides to resources*

46. American Library Association. Assistance in preparation of *Resources of American Libraries, 1950-1960* by Robert B. Downs. 1961; \$2,000; in progress.

47. Purdue Research Foundation. Publication and dissemination of *Masters' Theses in the Pure and Applied Sciences*, vol. 4. 1960; \$3,400; completed.

Beth M. Schick, editor: *Masters Theses in the Pure and Applied Sciences — 1959, Accepted by Colleges and Universities of the United States.* Lafayette, Indiana, Thermophysical Properties Research Center, School of Mechanical Engineering, Purdue University, v. IV, 1960. iv, 443 p. Processed.

II. *THROUGH IMPROVEMENT OF THE MEANS OF PHYSICAL ACCESS* (i.e., of the arrangements by which a book is made physically available to the user)

a. *Through improvement of the arrangements for acquisition*

i. *The Farmington Plan*

48. Princeton University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). Survey and evaluation of the Farmington Plan for the cooperative acquisition by American libraries of foreign publications of potential research value. 1957; \$12,400; completed.

Association of Research Libraries: *Farmington Plan Survey, Directed by Robert Vosper & Robert Talmadge, University of Kansas Libraries. Final Report Presented at the Midwinter*

Annual Meeting of ARL, Chicago, January 26, 1959. [Lawrence, Kansas, 1959] Various pagination [279 1.] Processed.

I. P. Gibb: Foreign Book Procurement. *Journal of Documentation*, 16: 1-9. March 1960.

Robert L. Talmadge: The Farmington Plan Survey; an Interim Report. *College and Research Libraries*, 19: 375-383. September 1958.

Robert Vosper: Farmington Redivivus: or Ten Years of Coordinated Foreign Book Procurement in the U.S. *Aslib Proceedings*, 11: 327-334. December 1959.

49. Princeton University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). Extension of the Farmington Plan. 1959; \$15,000; in progress.

Robert Vosper: International Book Procurement; or, Farmington Extended. *College and Research Libraries*, 21: 117-124. March 1960.

Edwin E. Williams: *What Is the Farmington Plan?* [Cambridge, Farmington Plan Committee of the Association of Research Libraries: December 1959] 4 p.

ii. The United States Book Exchange

50. The United States Book Exchange. A re-evaluation of its operations. 1958; \$14,280; completed.

Edwin E. Williams: *A Serviceable Reservoir; Report of a Survey of the United States Book Exchange.* Washington, The United States Book Exchange, Inc., 1959. 81 p.

—: The U.S.B.E. Survey. *Library Resources and Technical Services*, 4: 89-91. Winter 1960.

iii. Planning of photocopying projects

51. American Council of Learned Societies. An inquiry into the bases for planning scholarly photocopying projects. 1960; \$28,888; in progress.

52. Library of Congress. Toward expenses of a meeting to plan photocopying of European manuscript sources for American history. 1961; \$1,900; completed.

Dorothy S. Eaton and Marcia Wright: Conference to Plan Photocopying of European Manuscript Sources for American History. *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*, 20: 209-210. April 10, 1961.

iv. Reduction of trade barriers to the international flow of books

53. Pan American Union, General Secretariat, Organization of American States. For a study of obstacles to the free flow of publications (in the book trade) between the American Republics. 1959; \$1,000; completed.

54. Pan American Union, General Secretariat, Organization of American States. Further distribution of *Books in the Americas*. 1961; \$805; completed.

Peter S. Jennison and William H. Kurth: *Books in the Americas: A Study of the Principal Barriers to the Booktrade in the Americas*. Washington, Pan American Union, General Secretariat, Organization of American States, 1960. 165 p. Processed. (Estudios Bibliotecarios N. 2) [Second printing, 1961.] Also a Spanish-language edition, *El libro en America*.

v. *Library resources for Slavic studies*

55. Harvard University (on behalf of the Committee on Slavic and East European Studies of the Association of Research Libraries). Toward expenses of publication of *Russian and East European Publications in the Libraries of the United States*. 1959; \$2,940; completed.

Melville Ruggles and Vaclav Mostecky: *Russian and East European Publications in the Libraries of the United States*. New York, Columbia University Press, 1960. xv, 396 p. (Columbia University Studies in Library Service, No. 11.)

vi. *Use of "counterpart" funds for acquisition of foreign publications (Public Law 480)*

56. American Council of Learned Societies. For a report on progress in the implementation of Public Law 480. 1959; \$788; completed.

Mortimer Graves: A First Anniversary Report of Progress on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480 (Title I, Section 104n). *ACLS [American Council of Learned Societies] Newsletter*, 10: 8-12. November 1959.

—: *An Addendum Report on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480*. Key West, Florida, The Author. March 1960. 4 p.

—: *A Report of Modest Progress in the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to PL 480*. West Newbury, Massachusetts, The Author, August 20, 1961. 3 l. Processed.

b. *Through improved use of library storage space*

57. For a meeting to plan studies toward the solution of the space problems of large (general) research libraries. 1958; \$1,766; completed.

Meeting to Plan Studies Toward the Solution of the Space Problems of Large (General) Research Libraries. *Cosmos Club, Washington, D. C., October 27-28, 1958*. [Washington, Council on Library Resources, 1958.] 8 l. (and 1 l. of corrigenda Nov. 4). Processed.

Space Problems of Large (General) Research Libraries: Report of a Meeting. *College and Research Libraries*, 20: 217-220. May 1959.

58. Yale University. Development and demonstration of the basis, operation and results of the Yale University Library's Selective Book Retirement Program. 1959, 1960; \$150,000; in progress.

John H. Ottemiller, F. Bernice Field and Lee Ash: The Selective Book Retirement Program at Yale. *The Yale University Library Gazette*, 34: 64-72. October 1959.

59. University of Chicago. Study of patterns in the use of research library materials. 1959; \$84,600; in progress.

Herman H. Fussler and Julian L. Simon: *Patterns in the Use of Books in Large Research Libraries, Council on Library Resources, Inc., Grant 64*. [Chicago.] The University of Chicago Library, 1961. xi, 283, [42] p. Processed.

c. *Through improved preservation of library materials*

i. *Increasing the permanence/durability of book paper*

60. Virginia State Library. Deterioration of book-stock — causes and remedies. 1957; \$49,500; completed.

William J. Barrow: *Physical Strength of Non-Fiction Book Papers, 1900-1949. A Preliminary Report, December 1, 1957*. [Richmond, 1957.] [35 l.] Processed.

Randolph W. Church: Perish the Paper, Perish the Book, Perish the Thought: An Inquiry. *Publishers' Weekly*, 172: 54-58. September 2, 1957.

William J. Barrow: *Stabilization of Modern Book Papers, A Progress Report, June 1, 1958*. [Richmond, 1958.] 10 l. Processed.

61. For preparation of journal articles reporting on the results of No. 60; 1958; \$1,598; completed.

William J. Barrow and Reavis C. Sproull: Permanence in Book Papers. *Science*, 129: 1075-1084. April 24, 1959.

Randolph W. Church: Is There a Doctor in the House? *Publishers' Weekly*, 175: 76, 78-80. January 5, 1959.

62. Virginia State Library. Improvement of permanence and durability of book papers. 1959; \$38,465; completed.

William J. Barrow: *Improvement of Permanence and Durability of Book Papers, A Progress Report, June 24, 1959 - September 15, 1959, to Council on Library Resources*. [Richmond,] September 15, 1959. 32 l.

Randolph W. Church, editor: *Deterioration of Book Stock, Causes and Remedies: Two Studies on the Permanence of*

Book Paper Conducted by W. J. Barrow. Richmond, The Virginia State Library, 1959. 70 p.

—, editor: *The Manufacture and Testing of Durable Book Papers, Based on the Investigations of W. J. Barrow.* Richmond, The Virginia State Library, 1960. 63 p.

63. Conference on a Permanent/Durable Book Paper, Washington, D. C. September 16, 1960. 1960; \$2,929; completed.

Permanent/Durable Book Paper, Summary of a Conference Held in Washington, D. C., September 16, 1960. Sponsored by the American Library Association and the Virginia State Library. Richmond, The Virginia State Library, 1960. 53 p.

ii. Improvements in techniques and materials for binding and book repair

64. For a meeting to draft a program for development of performance standards for library binding. 1959; \$432; completed.

65. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Testing of certain adhesives and other materials used in book and manuscript preservation and repair. 1959; \$2,600; completed.

Gladys T. Piez: Laminator for Libraries. *ALA Bulletin*, 53: 269-175. March 1961.

66. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Miscellaneous testing (adhesives, copying paper, film coatings). 1960; \$1,000; completed.

67. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Development of performance standards for library binding, Phase I. 1960; \$18,926; completed.

[American Library Association, Research and Technical Services Division, Bookbinding Committee:] *Development of Performance Standards for Library Binding, Phase I, Report of the Survey Team, April 1961.* Chicago, American Library Association, Library Technology Project, 1961. vii, 62 p. (LTP Publications No. 2.)

68. Fred W. Alpers, Cleveland, Ohio. Investigation of European library binding practices. 1960; \$1,000; completed.

Fred W. Alpers: *Library Binding in Europe, Submitted to: Council on Library Resources, Inc. . . . Reported on January 16, 1961.* [iii.] 33 l. Typescript.

69. William J. Barrow, Richmond, Virginia. Preliminary investigation into aging of adhesives for "perfect" binding. 1961; \$4,000; completed.

Lee E. Grove: Predictability of Permanence in "Perfect" Library Bindings. *College and Research Libraries*, 22: 341-344. September 1961.

iii. Development of a national plan for preservation of deteriorating materials

70. Randolph W. Church, Virginia State Librarian. Inquiry to develop a plan of investigation of the life-expectancy of books in U.S. libraries. 1961; \$1,000; completed.
71. Cornell University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). Inquiry into the statistical bases for planning for the preservation of research library materials. 1961; \$2,350; in progress.

iv. Fire protection and insurance for libraries

72. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). A study of fire protection and insurance for libraries. 1960; \$50,000; in progress.

d. Through improved means of communicating recorded information

i. Systems for electronic telecommunication

73. University of Virginia. Demonstration of the use of closed-circuit TV in a decentralized library situation. 1957; \$39,419; completed.

Roger Bristol: *Card Turner Problems: A Preliminary Investigation of the Feasibility of Long-Distance Consultation of Card Catalogs*. Charlottesville, Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 12 l. Processed.

—: Closed-Circuit Television Experiment in a University Library. *Southeastern Librarian*, 8: 11-14. Spring 1958.

—: *Closed-Circuit TV Equipment as Used in a Decentralized Library Situation*. Charlottesville, Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 13 l. Processed.

—: *Microcard Images Transmitted by Closed-Circuit TV*. Charlottesville, Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 6 l. Processed.

—: *Page Turners: A Report of Their Usefulness for a Closed-Circuit TV Project*. Charlottesville, Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 14 l. Processed.

Frank Kenneth Gibson. *Closed-Circuit TV at the University of Virginia: A Summary Report*. Charlottesville, Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1959. 7 l. Processed.

University of Virginia, Bureau of Public Administration: *A Report on an Experiment Involving the Use of Closed-Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation*. [Charlottesville,] The Bureau, 1958. v, 31 l., pl. Processed.

74. Image Instruments, Inc. First phase investigation of electronic systems applicable for improving library service in a metropolitan area, parts 1-3. 1960, 1961; \$13,463; in progress.

ii. Reading matter for the blind

75. Library of Congress. Pilot project demonstration of production of encapsulated tape-recorded books for the blind. 1960; \$50,000; in progress.
76. Recording for the Blind, Inc. Pilot project demonstration of service of encapsulated tape-recorded books for the blind. 1960; \$12,000; in progress.

Lee E. Grove: Reading for the Blind at a New Frontier. *ALA Bulletin*, 53: 744. September 1961.

e. Through improvement of copying techniques and applications (general)

i. Exploration of materials and processes for dry photocopying

77. Lyman Chalkley, Washington, D. C. Investigation of dye cyanides and other dry-process photosensitive materials. 1958; \$2,000; completed.

Lyman Chalkley: Conditions for Projection Copying on Dye Cyanide Sensitized Materials. *Photographic Science and Engineering*, 3: 174-177. July-August 1959.

78. W. C. Huebner. New York. For a demonstration model of Migrafax. 1958; \$2,000; completed.

79. Eugene Garfield Associates, Philadelphia. For development of an experimental model of the "Copywriter." 1958; \$9,102; completed.

[Eugene Garfield Associates:] *Final Report on the Development of a First Model of the Copywriter*. Philadelphia, The Company, April 20, 1960. 11 l. Typescript.

ii. An automatic book-cradle/page-turner for use in photocopying, telefacsimile, etc.

80. Radio Corporation of America. Design Plan for an automatic book-cradle/page-turner. 1958; \$5,000; completed.

Radio Corporation of America, Development Engineering, Defense Electronic Products: *Design Plan for the Development of an Automatic Page Turner by Elbert Marsh, August 1958*. Camden, New Jersey, The Corporation, 1958. 25 l., 17 pl. Processed.

81. The de Florez Company. Design plan for an automatic book-cradle/page-turner. 1958. \$5,000; completed.

The de Florez Company, Inc.: *Report on Design Study of a Book Cradle/Page Turner*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey, The Company, 1959. 18 l., 5 pl. Processed.

82. The de Florez Company. Construction of a working model of an automatic book-cradle/page-turner. 1959, 1960, 1961; \$35,000; in progress.

iii. Other devices for facilitating copying

83. American Library Association. Testing of book-copying equipment, Phase I. 1960; \$30,000; in progress. (Funded under No. 129.)
84. The de Florez Company. Development of a pilot model of a book-copying cradle/press. 1961; \$6,500; in progress.
85. Bell & Howell Company. Fabrication of the prototype of a scholar's camera. 1961; \$9,687; in progress.

iv. Legal problems involved in photocopying in libraries

86. New York Public Library (on behalf of the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying). For legal studies of photocopying in libraries. 1959, 1961; \$18,877; completed. Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying: Report on Single Copies. *Special Libraries*, 52: 251-255. May-June 1961.
- Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying: Fair Use in Photocopying, Report on Single Copies. *ALA Bulletin*, 55: 571-573. June 1961.

f. Through more effective use of microcopy

i. Planning

87. For a meeting to plan steps toward improvement of the applications of microphotography to library work. 1958; \$1,682; completed.
- Meeting on the Problems of Microform in Libraries, Cosmos Club, Washington, D. C., May 23, 1958; Summary of Discussions.* Washington, Council on Library Resources, Inc. [1958]. 12 l., processed.

ii. Standardization and improvement of practice

88. American Library Association. Preparation of a new edition of *Guide to Microfilming Practices*. 1961; \$1,000; in progress.

iii. Dissemination of information regarding equipment for using microcopy in libraries

89. National Microfilm Association. Demonstration of microcopying techniques, equipment and applications and publication of the Guide to *Equipment for Microreproduction*. 1958; \$10,330; completed.

Hubbard W. Ballou: *Guide to Microreproduction Equipment*. Annapolis, National Microfilm Association, 1959. viii, 438 p. First Supplement to the *Guide*, April 1960; Second Supplement, April 1961. (Subsequent information in *The National Micro-News*, official journal of the Association.)

iv. Experimental publication in microform

90. American Institute of Biological Sciences. For the experimental publication of a scientific journal (*Wildlife Disease*, the journal of the Wildlife Disease Association) in microform. 1958; \$11,274; in progress.

Carlton M. Herman: New Journal in Microform. *A.I.B.S.* [American Institute of Biological Sciences] *Bulletin*, 9: 31-33, January 1959.

Proposed Journal Becomes an Actuality. *Wildlife Disease Association Newsletter*, 19: 1-4. November 1958.

Wildlife Disease No. 1 — [Washington, Wildlife Disease Association], January 1959. [Quarterly; issued on Microcards with accompanying leaflet, "Abstracts from *Wildlife Disease*."]]

v. Application of microphotography to problems of distribution and storage

91. Intectron, Inc. Investigation of factors affecting high-reduction photography. 1960; \$31,756; in progress.
92. AVCO Manufacturing Corporation. Development of an experimental high-density direct-access photostorage-and-retrieval system for library materials. 1958; \$201,531; completed.

AVCO Corporation, Crosley Division, Electronics Research Laboratories: *Technical Investigation of Elements of a Mechanized Library System, Special Report No. EW 6680-1, August 18, 1959*. Boston, The Corporation, 1959. 18 l. Processed.

K. Bowker, L. H. Martin, E. J. Lucas and C. Phaneuf: *Technical Investigations of Elements of a Mechanized Library System, Final Report No. EW-6680, January 11, 1960*. Boston, Electronics Research Laboratories, Crosley Division, AVCO Corporation, 1960. vi, 110 p. Processed. Second printing: Cincinnati, Electronics and Ordnance Division, AVCO Corporation, [1961].

93. AVCO Manufacturing Corporation. Addition of hard-copy print-out equipment to the high-density photographic store. 1960; \$58,847; in progress.
94. Forbes & Waite. Preliminary investigation of technological/economic factors involved in miniaturizing research library collections. 1961; \$2,500; in progress.

vi. Development of devices for individual private use of microtext

95. Microcard Corporation. Prototypes of hand-reading devices for microtext. 1957; \$12,515; completed.
96. John R. Miles Company. Preliminary investigation toward designing a magnifier to be used in a hand-viewer for microtext. 1958; \$499; completed.

97. John R. Miles Company. For development toward the design of a 20x magnifier for reading microtext. 1958; \$16,706; completed.
98. John R. Miles Company. Development of a 13x magnifier. 1959; \$5,033; completed.
99. John R. Miles Company. Photographic tests of various magnifiers. 1960; \$214; completed.
100. John R. Miles Company. Development of a 10x-30x (variable) microscope-magnifier for reading microtext. 1960, 1961; \$11,000; in progress.
Verner W. Clapp: In Quest of an Optical "Grail." *ALA Bulletin*, 55: 164-167. February 1961.
101. Battelle Memorial Institute. Investigations looking to improved methods of viewing microimages. 1960; \$49,200; in progress.

vii. Development of devices for producing microcopies

102. Vernon D. Tate. Investigation of methods for making sheet microfilm (microfiche). 1959; \$3,000; in progress.
103. Bell & Howell Company. Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography. 1960; \$177,209; in progress.

g. Through improvement of equipment for physical display

104. American Library Association. Development of an improved newspaper stick. 1960; \$12,500; in progress. (Funded under No 129.)

III. IMPROVEMENT OF THE ADMINISTRATIVE BASES OF LIBRARY WORK (i.e., of the organizational, fiscal, structural and other supporting facilities)

a. Through regional organization of resources and interlibrary cooperation

105. Harry J. Krould, Silver Spring, Maryland. Study and report on the possibilities for regional coordination of library reference services. 1958; \$10,315; completed.

Harry J. Krould: *An Inquiry on Aspects of Public Library Reference Service*. [Washington, 1958] 2 v. Typescript.

106. The Brookings Institution. A survey of Federal libraries. 1959; \$72,965; in progress.

Luther H. Evans: The Survey of Federal Departmental Libraries. *D. C. Libraries*, 31: 2-8. January 1960.

107. Brown University. For a study in support of a project in university-community-school library coordination. 1960; \$24,000; in progress.

Elmer R. Smith: *Library Developments in Rhode Island. Addresses Delivered at the New England Library Conference, New Ocean House, Swampscott, Massachusetts, October 7, 1960.* Providence, Public Library Services in Rural Areas, Rhode Island Department of State, 1960. p. 21-31.

108. American Library Association. To plan a study of the problems of metropolitan area library service. 1960; \$1,629; completed.

109. Bowdoin College. A survey of the possibilities of cooperation among principal Maine libraries (Bowdoin, Bates and Colby colleges; University of Maine; Bangor and Portland public libraries; Maine State Library). 1960; \$3,663; completed.

Keyes D. Metcalf: *Cooperation Among Maine Libraries, A Report Prepared for the Larger Libraries of Maine.* Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1961. 22 p.

b. *Through improved administrative and public relations of libraries*

i. *Preparation of procedural manuals*

110. American Library Association. Assistance to small community libraries. 1960; \$60,040; in progress.

ii. *Promotion of the use of library services*

111. University of Michigan. Toward the expenses of the National Conference on the Undergraduate and the Lifetime Reading Habit, February 21-22, 1958. 1957; \$3,842; completed.

Jacob M. Price, editor: *Reading for Life: Developing the College Student's Lifetime Reading Interest.* Ann Arbor, University of Michigan Press, [1959]. xi, 271 p. (Record of the Conference.)

112. National Book Committee. Toward the Expenses of National Library Week: 1959, 1960. 1958, 1960; \$20,000; completed.

National Book Committee, Inc.: *Report on the First Observance of National Library Week. Recognition and Response.* [New York, The Committee, 1959.] 16 p.

—: *1959 National Library Week. 2nd Annual Report.* [New York, the Committee, 1959.] [22 p.]

—: *For a Better-Read, Better-Informed America, 1960 National Library Week, 3rd Annual Report.* [New York, The Committee, 1960.] 24 p.

—: *Open Wonderful New Worlds . . . Wake Up and Read! National Library Week Organization Handbook*. [New York, The Committee, 1960.] 56 p.

iii. Exploration of sources of support

113. Boston Athenaeum. Study of the independent historical societies. 1958; \$20,000; in progress.

Walter Muir Whitehill: In My Father's House Are Many Mansions. *The American Archivist*, 24: 133-139. April 1961.

114. Cornell University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). Establishment of a formula for library overhead in Government contract research. 1960; \$3,000; completed.

iv. Implementation of standards of library service

115. American Library Association. Implementation of the 1960 School Library Standards. 1960; \$100,000; in progress.

American Association of School Librarians: *Report[s] of the School Library Development Project*. Chicago, The Association, 1961-. Processed.

v. Demonstration and exhibits of library services

116. American Library Association. Inquiry into the feasibility of preparing an exhibit of "the library of the future" for the Century 21 Exposition, Seattle, 1962. 1960; \$2,000; completed.

117. American Library Association. Preparation of plans for a "library of the future" for the Century 21 Exposition, Seattle, 1962. 1960; \$30,991; in progress.

c. Through improved planning of library buildings and furniture

118. American Library Association (co-sponsor with the Association of Research Libraries). Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings. 1959; \$73,365; in progress.

Keyes D. Metcalf: Alternatives to a New Library Building. *College and Research Libraries*, 22: 345-354. September 1961.

119. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Evaluation of methods for testing library furniture. 1961; \$3,637; in progress.

d. Through improvement of circulation and other records systems

120. John Diebold & Associates. Inquiry into problems relating to book charging systems. 1959; \$6,407; completed.

John Diebold & Associates, Inc.: *Preliminary Study of Library Circulation Systems for the Council on Library Resources, October 1959*. [New York,] The Corporation, 1959. 31 l. Processed. (Also issued as a Microcard.)

121. George Fry & Associates. A study of circulation control in libraries. 1960; \$94,100; completed.

George Fry & Associates, Inc.: *Study of Circulation Control Systems, Public Libraries, College and University Libraries, Special Libraries*. Chicago, Library Technology Project of the American Library Association and the Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1961. 138 p. (Three sections — Circulation System Selection Manual for Public Libraries, Circulation System Selection Manual for College and University Libraries, Circulation Control for Special Libraries — have also been published separately.)

122. American Library Association. Advisory services in connection with the study of circulation control in libraries. 1960; \$6,800; in progress.
123. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Construction of a prototype borrower-participation book-charging device (the "Little Giant"). 1961; \$1,000; completed.
124. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Publication and implementation of the report of the study of circulation control. 1961; \$21,802; completed.
125. Ralph Blasingame, Jr., Harrisburg, Pennsylvania. Study of the application of machine-sorted punched cards to selected library routines. 1960; \$2,450; in progress.

e. *Through standardizing and testing of supplies, equipment and systems*

126. American Library Association. Library Technology; a feasibility study. 1957; \$12,682; completed.

John H. Ottemiller: *Library Technology: A Feasibility Study. Report of the Director*. Chicago, American Library Association, 1958. 29 p. Processed.

—: A Program for Upgrading Systems and Procedures. *Library Journal*, 84: 1041-1047. April 1, 1959.

127. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). A program of testing and standardization of library equipment, supplies and systems. 1958; \$136,395; completed.

Richard B. Harwell: The Library Technology Project. *ALA Bulletin*, 53: 195-196. March 1959.

Library Technology Project, American Library Association: *First Annual Report, Period Ending April 30, 1960*. [Chicago, 1960. 20 p.]

128. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Miscellaneous testing projects. 1960; \$5,000; completed.
129. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). For support of projects to be submitted from time to time. 1960; \$100,000; in progress.
Frazer G. Poole. The Library Technology Project. *College and Research Libraries*, 22: 366-368, 374. September 1961.
130. American Library Association (Library Technology Project). Extension of Library Technology Project. 1961; \$210,652; in progress.
131. Sidney Hollander, Jr., Associates. Survey of accomplishment of the Library Technology Project. 1960; \$7,000; completed.
Sidney Hollander, Jr., Associates: *The Librarian and the Library Technology Project*. Baltimore, The Company, December 1960. 45 l. Processed.

f. *Through improved training for librarianship and use of manpower*

132. For a meeting of the Committee on a Survey of Library Education of the Joint Committee on Library Education of the Council of National Library Associations. 1958; \$562; completed.
133. Emory University. Toward the preparation of a new edition of *The Administration of the College Library* by Guy R. Lyle. 1960; \$2,000; completed.
Guy R. Lyle, with the collaboration of Paul H. Bixler, Marjorie Hood and Arnold H. Trotier: *The Administration of the College Library*. New York, H. W. Wilson Company, 1961. 419 p.

IV. FACT-FINDING AND PLANNING FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

a. *In library work generally*

134. Rutgers University, Graduate School of Library Service. Targets for research in library work. 1957; \$94,769; completed.
The State of the Library Art. New Brunswick, New Jersey, Graduate School of Library Service, Rutgers—The State University, 1960-1961. Ralph R. Shaw, series editor: Volume 1, Part 1, *Cataloging and Classification*, by Maurice F. Tauber, 271 p.; Part 2, *Subject Headings*, by Carlyle J. Frarey, 92 p. Volume 2, Part 1, *Training Laymen in Use of the Library*, by George S. Bonn, 114 p.; Part 2, *Bibliographies, Abstracts and Indexes*, by Margaret S. Bryant, 108 p. Volume 2, Part 3, *Charging Systems*, by Leila H. Kirkwood, 397 p. Volume 3,

Part 1, *Buildings*, by Ralph E. Ellsworth, 151 p.; Part 2, *Shelving*, by Louis Kaplan, 41 p.; Part 3, *Storage Warehouses*, by Jerrold Orne, 52 p. Volume 4, Part 1, *Notched Cards*, by Felix Reichman[n]; Part 2, *Feature Cards (Peek-a-Book [sic] Cards)*, by Lawrence S. Thompson; Part 3, *Punched Cards*, by Ralph Blasingame, Jr.; Part 4, *Electronic Searching*, by Gerald Jahoda; Part 5, *Coding in Yes-No Form*, by Doralyn J. Hickey; 373 p. Volume 5, Part 1, *Production of Micro-Forms*, by Reginald Hawkins, 208 p. Volume 5, Part 2, *Reading Devices for Micro-Images*, by Jean Stewart, Doralyn Hickey and others, 205 p. Volume 5, Part 3, *Full-Size Photocopying*, by William R. Hawken, 397 p.

135. American Library Association. Library resources fact-finding survey. 1957; \$12,125; in progress.

Mary Virginia Gaver: *Every Child Needs a School Library*. [Chicago, American Library Association, 1958.] 16 p.

Flora B. Ludington: *Books and Libraries . . . Tools of the Academic World*. [Chicago, American Library Association, 1958.] 15 p.

Arthur H. Parsons, Jr.: *Fountains, Not Reservoirs — The Public Library*. [Chicago, American Library Association, 1958.] 16 p.

136. For a planning meeting under the auspices of the Council of National Library Associations, January 11-13, 1961. 1960; \$1,494; completed.

137. Alton H. Keller (on behalf of the Agenda Committee, Assembly of State Librarians). Toward the expenses of the first meeting of the Assembly. 1958; \$400; completed.

F. Evelyn Crown, editor: *Summary Proceedings of the Assembly of State Librarians, held at the Library of Congress, November 12-14, 1958*. Washington, Library of Congress, 1959. v, 45 p. Processed.

138. Assembly of State Librarians, Agenda Committee. Toward the expenses of the second meeting of the Assembly. 1960; \$1,000; completed.

James R. Bowman, editor: *Proceedings of the Second Assembly of State Librarians, held at the Library of Congress, November 16-18, 1960*. Washington, Library of Congress, 1961. [vi,] 72 p. Processed.

139. For a meeting to develop a nation-wide plan for metropolitan library service. 1961; \$650; completed.

140. University of Illinois (*Library Trends* revolving fund). To procure computations of data resulting from the 1960 Census for use in an issue of *Library Trends* on demographic aspects of library work. 1960; \$700; in progress.

141. Meeting of the panel to review the program of the Council on Library Resources. 1958; \$1,865; completed.

142. Expenses of review of the program of the Council on Library Resources. 1960; \$6,525; completed.

b. *In college and university libraries*

143. Meetings of the Joint Committee of the Association of American Colleges and of the Association of College and Research Libraries. 1958, 1960; \$1,311; completed.

c. *In research libraries*

144. New York Public Library. For a project of its choosing in the interest of improvement of research library service. 1961; \$5,000; in progress.

d. *In interlibrary cooperation*

145. Columbia University (on behalf of the Library Schools Committee on Research in Interlibrary Cooperation). To aid in the planning of research by the Committee. 1958; \$3,909; completed.

146. Andrew D. Osborn, Sydney, New South Wales. Travel in the United States to develop exchange arrangements and other forms of interlibrary cooperation. 1959; \$1,000; completed.

e. *In international aspects*

147. Sergius Yakobson, Boris I. Gorokhoff and Paul L. Horecky. Preparation of *Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union and Publishing in the USSR*. 1957, 1958, 1959; \$12,357; completed.

148. Toward expenses of publication of the books resulting from No. 147. 1959; \$4,838; completed.

Boris I. Gorokhoff: *Publishing in the U.S.S.R.* [Bloomington, Indiana University Publications, 1959.] xvi, 306 p. (Graduate School Slavic and East European Series, v. 19.)

Paul L. Horecky: *Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union*. [Bloomington, Indiana University Publications, 1959.] xviii, 287 p. (Graduate School Slavic and East European Series, v. 16.)

149. Edward J. Carter, London. Report on a basis for more effective participation of American librarians in the program of the International Federation of Library Associations. 1958; \$500; completed.

Edward Carter: *International Organization in Librarianship and Documentation*. [Washington, 1958.] 59 l. Processed.

150. Library of Congress. To enable the Librarian of Congress to participate in the Unesco-sponsored Symposium on National Libraries in Europe, Vienna, September 8-27, 1958. 1958; \$3,000; completed.

[L. Quincy Mumford:] Report from the Librarian of Congress [on the Symposium on National Libraries of Europe, Vienna, September 1958]. *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*, 17: 611-612. October 27, 1958.

- f. *With respect to applications of mathematics, mechanical and electronic devices to library work*

151. National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council. Assistance toward the International Conference on Scientific Information, Washington, D. C., November 1958. 1958; \$15,000; completed.

International Conference on Scientific Information: *Proceedings*, Washington, D. C., November 16-21, 1958. Washington, National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council, 1959. 2 v. 1639 p.

152. National Science Foundation. Toward the first two years' expenses of the National Bureau of Standards Research Information Center and Advisory Service on Information Processing. 1958; \$20,000; completed.

B. K. Bender, A. J. Goldman and R. B. Thomas: *Computer Simplification of Boolean Functions*. Washington, U.S. National Bureau of Standards, 1960, ii, 45 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)

Richard S. Glantz: *Further Investigation of English Syntax with the Theory of Syntactic Types*. Washington, U.S. National Bureau of Standards, 1959, ii, 18 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)

Ethel Marden: *A Survey of Computer Programs for Chemical Information Searching*. Washington, U.S. National Bureau of Standards, 1960, ii, 56, 27 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)

M. E. Stevens: *Automatic Character Recognition: A State-of-the-Art Report*. Washington, U.S. National Bureau of Standards, 1961, viii, 236 p. Processed. (Unpublished.) Appendix: *Bibliography on Character Recognition*, by F. Y. Neeland and M. E. Stevens. Washington, U.S. National Bureau of Standards, 1961, 57 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)

The Domain of Information Selection and Retrieval Research. Washington, U.S. National Bureau of Standards, Research Information Center and Advisory Services on Information Processing, Data Processing Systems Division, 1960, ii, 32 p. Washington, 1960, ii, 33 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)

U.S. National Bureau of Standards, Research Information Center and Advisory Service on Information Processing:

- First Annual Report.* Washington, 1959. ii, 25 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)
- : *A Framework for Basic Research on Mechanized Information Storage, Search and Selection.* Washington, 1960. ii, 22 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)
- : *General Aspects of Storage of Scientific Information.* Washington, 1960. ii, 33 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)
- : *Suggested Topics for State-of-the-Art Reviews.* Washington, 1960. ii, 13 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)
- : *Syntactic Techniques in Information Retrieval.* Washington, 1960. i, 13 p. Processed. (Unpublished.)
153. National Bureau of Standards. For a state-of-the-art review of mechanized information selection and retrieval systems, especially those employing photographic storage. 1961; \$25,000; in progress.
154. University of Illinois (Chicago Undergraduate Division). Investigation of possible applications of advanced data processing techniques to university library procedures. 1960; \$50,000; in progress.
155. Library of Congress. Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries. 1960, 1961; \$100,000; in progress.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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This report has been designed by the George Lohr Studio, Washington.

APPENDIX B
FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Accountant's Opinion

September 22, 1961

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1961 and the expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1961

ASSETS

Cash	\$ 309,818
Investments, at cost plus discount earned (approximate market):	
United States Treasury Bills, due August 10, 1961	99,751
United States Treasury Bills, due July 15, 1961	1,248,395
Deposits	475
	\$1,658,439

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable, per accompanying statement	\$1,009,805
Accounts payable	4,734
Fund balance (Notes 1 and 2):	
Balance June 30, 1960	\$2,267,400
Expenditures less income for the year, per accompanying statement	1,623,500
Balance June 30, 1961	643,900
	\$1,658,439

(1) The Ford Foundation has approved an additional grant of \$8,000,000 effective July 1, 1961 to the Council on Library Resources, Inc. in order that the Council may continue for a seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular.

(2) As at June 30, 1961, \$1,153,550 had been appropriated but not yet awarded for certain grants and contracts. A substantial portion of these appropriations was made by the Council after receiving notification from The Ford Foundation of the grant which became effective July 1, 1961.

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1961

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects, per accompanying statement	\$1,557,293	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded, per accompanying statement	23,055	\$1,534,238

General administrative expense

Compensation and employee benefits	117,890	
Rent	6,910	
Professional services	3,564	
Travel and meetings	13,761	
Furniture and equipment	725	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	15,298	158,148
		\$1,692,386

INCOME

From investments	68,886	
Expenditures less income		\$1,623,500

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1961

	Payable June 30, 1960	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1961
Alpers, Fred W. Investigation of European library binding prac- tices		\$ 1,000		\$ 1,000	
American Association of Law Libraries A mechanized compilation of a list of legal sub- ject headings	\$ 5,000			5,000	
American Institute of Biological Sciences Experimental publication of a scientific journal in microform	2,500			2,500	
American Library Association Assistance in preparation of Resources of American Libraries, 1950-1960		2,000		2,000	
Assistance to small community libraries.....		60,040		60,040	
Assistance toward ALA Catalog Code Revision Project		8,900		8,900	
Implementation of the 1960 School Library Standards		100,000		25,000	\$ 75,000
Library Technology Project Additional projects of testing library sup- plies, equipment and systems.....	91,000			66,452 (850)	24,548
Development of a book-marking system....		1,000	\$ 1,850		
Development of performance standards for library binding—Phase I		18,926		18,926	
Engineering and construction of a prototype borrower-operated book-charging machine.		1,000		1,000	
Evaluation of methods for testing wood library furniture		3,636		3,636	
Extension of Library Technology Project....		210,652		38,075	172,577
Program of testing and standardization of library supplies, equipment and systems..	76,395			76,395	
Publication of the report of the study of book circulation systems		21,802			21,802
Study of fire protection and insurance in libraries		50,000		50,000	
Planning a "Library of the Future" exhibit for the Century 21 Exposition, Seattle 1962...		30,991		25,000	5,991
Preparation of a new edition of the Guide to Microfilming Practices		1,000		1,000	
Reprint of Sharify: Cataloging of Persian Works		975		975	
Review and evaluation of the operation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.....		1,175		1,175	
Travel grants to promote the international co- ordination of cataloging rules.....			150	(150)	
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries) Preparation of a book on the planning of col- lege/university library buildings	35,365				35,365

	Payable June 30, 1960	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1961
Assembly of State Librarians, Agenda Committee Assistance to Second Assembly of State Li- brarians, Washington, D. C., November 16-18, 1960		\$ 1,000		\$ 1,000	
Avco Corporation Addition of hard copy output to the high-density photographic store		58,847			\$ 58,847
Barrow, William J. Preliminary investigation into aging of adhe- sives for "perfect" binding		4,000	\$ 1	3,999	
Battelle Memorial Institute Investigations looking to improved viewing of microimages		49,200		32,800	16,400
Bell & Howell Company Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography..... Fabrication of prototype of a scholar's camera.		177,209 9,687		22,606	154,603 9,687
Blasingame, Jr., Ralph Study of the application of machine-sorted punched cards to selected library routines..		2,450		2,450	
Bowdoin College A survey of possibilities of cooperation among principal Maine libraries			1,337	(1,337)	
Brookings Institution A survey of federal government libraries.....	\$34,978			34,978	
Brown University A study in support of university-school-com- munity library coordination	12,000				12,000
Church, Randolph W. Inquiry to develop a plan of investigation into the life expectancy of books in U.S. libraries.		1,004		1,004	
Columbia University (on behalf of the Library Schools Committee on Research on Interli- brary Cooperation) To aid in the planning of research by the Li- brary Schools Committee on Research and Interlibrary Cooperation			1,701	(1,701)	
Conference on a Permanent/Durable Book Paper, Washington, D. C., September 16, 1960*.....		5,000	2,071	2,929	
Cornell University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries) Statistical basis for planning the preservation of research library materials.....		2,350		2,350	
The de Florez Company, Inc. Construction of a working model of an auto- matic book-cradle/page-turner	6,194	15,000		18,547	2,647
Conditions-testing model of a catalog card duplicator		15,000		9,025	5,975
Development of a pilot model of a book-copying cradle/press		6,500			6,500
Development of an improved stencil duplicator for catalog cards	1,714			1,714	

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1960	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1961
Development of a continuing book-selection service for college libraries*		\$ 1,000		\$ 100	\$ 900
Forbes & Waite					
Preliminary investigation of physical/economic factors involved in miniaturizing research library collections		2,500			2,500
George Fry & Associates, Inc.					
Study of book-circulation systems	\$ 77,500	16,600		93,345	755
Sidney Hollander Associates					
Survey of accomplishment of Library Technology Project		7,000		7,000	
Image Instruments, Inc.					
First phase investigation of the applicability of electronic systems to library service in metropolitan areas, Parts I, II and III	5,000	9,800	\$ 1,337	11,278	2,185
Intectron, Incorporated					
Investigations of factors affecting high-reduction microphotography		31,756		9,065	22,691
International Association of Music Libraries (on behalf of the International Joint Commission on the International Repertory of Music Sources)					
For support of work on the Repertory		14,000		14,000	
International Federation of Library Associations					
An international conference on the principles of cataloging, 1961	85,420			10,000	75,420
Johns Hopkins University					
Interim assistance to Economics Library Selections as a book-selection service to college libraries		2,000		2,000	
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc.					
Assistance toward placing the record of serials in libraries in the United States and Canada on a continuing basis (3rd Edition of the Union List of Serials, etc.)	144,651			144,651	
Jonker Business Machines, Inc.					
Development of equipment for an inexpensive disseminable mechanical system for searching legal literature — Phase I		41,000		3,270	37,730
Library of Congress					
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections	100,000			100,000	
Meeting to plan photocopying of European manuscript sources for American history		1,900		1,900	
Pilot project demonstration of tape-recorded books for the blind		50,000		50,000	
Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries		100,000		30,000	70,000
Massachusetts Institute of Technology					
Feasibility study of the design of an automatic catalog card replicator		14,238			14,238

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1960	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1961
Meeting on preparation of a nation-wide plan for metropolitan library service*.....		\$ 650		\$ 218	\$ 432
Meeting on program planning for the Council of National Library Associations*.....		3,000	\$ 1,506	1,494	
John R. Miles Company					
Development of a 10x-30x compound microscope for reading micro-opaques		11,000		10,378	622
Development of a 13x magnifier for reading micro-opaques	\$ 142		142		
Photographic tests of various magnifiers.....		500	286	214	
Music Library Association					
For travel in connection with representation at the International Conference on Cataloging Principles, Paris, October, 1961.....		1,500		1,500	
National Bureau of Standards					
State-of-the-art-review of mechanized information selection and facsimile retrieval systems		25,000		25,000	
New York Public Library					
For a project of its choosing in the interest of reference and research library service.....		5,000		5,000	
New York Public Library (on behalf of the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying)					
For legal studies of photocopying in libraries..		14,877		14,877	
Pan American Union					
Assistance toward publication of Books in the Americas		805		805	
Purdue Research Foundation (on behalf of the Thermophysical Properties Research Center, Purdue University)					
Publication and distribution of Masters' Theses in the Pure and Applied Sciences, Vol. 4...		3,400		3,400	
Project Lawsearch (The Michie Company, Matthew Bender & Company, Inc. and The Bureau of National Affairs, Inc.)					
Development of a disseminable, mechanical information search system for legal literature		40,000		11,000	29,000
Recording for the Blind, Inc.					
Pilot project demonstration of tape-recorded books for the blind		12,000		12,000	
Review of Council on Library Resources, Inc., program*	3,550		3,475	75	
Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.					
Studies in word correlation and automatic indexing, Phases I and IIA	16,585	78,237	5,615	41,860	47,347
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	34,600			10,000	24,600

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1960	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1961
University of Illinois					
Investigation of applicability of advanced data processing techniques to university library procedures		\$50,000		\$50,000	
The 1960 Census and its implications for libraries		300		300	
University of Pittsburgh					
Searching statutory law by computer		58,886		29,443	\$29,443
Virginia State Library					
Improvement of permanence and durability of book papers			\$3,584	(3,584)	
Yale University					
Development and demonstration of the basis, operation and results of the Yale University Library's selective book retirement program.		100,000		50,000	50,000
Totals	\$732,594	\$1,557,293	\$23,055	\$1,257,027	\$1,009,805

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Book
Acc.

United States
Military Academy
Library

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